

METHODOLOGY FOR INNOVATIVE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Musayeva Muhabbat Eshbayevna works as an associate professor at the department of "Educational Technologies" at the network (regional) center for retraining and professional development of pedagogues under the National University of Uzbekistan.

Qisqacha mazmun: Ushbu maqolada ta'lim jarayonini raqamli va pedagogik texnologiyalarga asoslangan holda fanlarni o'qitishda o'quv jarayonini samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari va ulardan foydalanish afzalliklari yoritilgan.

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны возможности и преимущества использования образовательного процесса, призванного повысить эффективность образовательного процесса при преподавании предметов на основе цифровых и педагогических технологий.

Annotation: This article highlights the possibilities and advantages of using the educational process designed to improve the effectiveness of the educational process when teaching subjects based on digital and pedagogical technologies.

Between the various characteristics necessary for the need able parts of the professional activity of a modern teacher, it is often called a creative approach to pedagogical activity. To do this, at the university, it is necessary to create a creative personality, played with flexible productivity, which allows you to create various original, model ideas at the stage of training future teachers. Creativity is the essence of various types of human activity; it is as specific to a person as consciousness, thinking, imagination, etc. This is the position of human thinking, which has a characteristic feature for the versatile, changeable appearance of the individual. That a modern teacher should be in fact, the success of the reforms carried out in the educational system directly depends on the professional skills and literacy of the teaching staff. The teacher is a person who has a special education in his/her specialty in pedagogical and psychological terms, has professional training and high moral qualities, operates in educational institutions. To be aware of the latest knowledge in their specialty, to organize education using pedagogical technologies and Information Technologies on the basis of the laws of the current educational and educational process, to demonstrate their skills, knowledge and abilities, to take into account the age and psychological characteristics of learners in education, to create conditions for the assimilation of knowledge by them, taking into, it is necessary to activate the comprehensive maturation of the individual.

If we consider effective educational technologies and interactive learning techniques that are used in higher grades in secondary schools.

Problem education is based on the creation of different problem situations in educational activities that should activate the independence of students. As a result, analytical and creative mastery and abilities develop. Multi-level training helps the teacher to help vulnerable students and focus on strengths. This technique creates the desire for more capable students to develop deeper in the field of education, while the rest of the students achieve academic success, which increases learning motivation.

Design-based teaching methods develop the creative potential of schoolchildren, forcing them to consciously determine professional and social fate. Research methods of teaching allow students to independently study the problems of interest to them and suggest ways to solve them. The essence of group training in teaching a new topic does not come from the requirements of the curriculum, however from the capabilities of the student. In-group classes, psychological and

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pedagogical diagnostics of the individual are widely used. In the upper classes, lecture and credit technology are used. This gives schoolchildren the opportunity to prepare for university studies. The essence of this system is to provide knowledge in one block, the management of which is carried out depending on the initial training of students. The innovative portfolio assessment system is based on the formation of a personal account of the student's success as a means of determining the direction of Personality Development. Nowadays, digital and Information and communication technologies in the educational process are an endless enrichment of knowledge through the use of computers and the Internet. The introduction of new methods and technologies into the educational system does not at all mean the abolition of traditional teaching methods. Innovation is an integral part of the entire learning process. The usage of information and communication technologies not only increases the effectiveness of Professional activity, but also has its positive effect on the formation of a worldview and Information Culture in future specialists, their lifestyle, activities in the social sphere. For the use of information and communication technologies in the educational system of our republic, educational institutions are sufficiently provided with all technical means. During the period when such conditions are created, teachers are required to use modern information and communication technologies in the educational process. In all forms and types of institutions of the continuing education system of the Republic, the educational and educational process can be achieved by creating modern conditions of training, with full scientific and methodological support.

The future of the country largely depends on what, how and to what extent the youth's thirst for knowledge is satisfied by educators in educational institutions today. It is among the complex works that depend on a large number of factors to cope with this task as it requires, as it pleases, the period. To do this, first of all, you should have the qualities of love and dedication to your work in the teacher who performs this work. Only when our high level of knowledge and experience is combined with the above-mentioned qualities can a certain positive result be achieved in each lesson session that is held. In the educational system, computer technology is the main tool in the use of information and communication technologies in the first place. On the basis of computer equipment, there are options for collecting, storing, processing information resources and using electronic and virtual libraries. Secondly, the educational system uses special software tools for creating multimedia electronic educational literature, lecture notes, virtual laboratory work and various animation developments. One such software tool is pedagogical software tools. Pedagogical software tools are a didactic tool designed to completely or partially automate the educational process using computer technology. They are considered one of the promising forms of increasing the effectiveness of the educational process and are used as a modern teaching tool.

The importance of pedagogical technologies and Information Communication Technologies in the educational process in the self study of students studying using practical and online programs is as follows:

- forms the knowledge, skills and abilities of the student;
- serves as a form of education that increases the degree of assimilation of the student in the subjects;
- the teacher's advice and recommendations, the scope of preparation for the assimilation of knowledge will be made possible by the implementation of it in the audience or outside the audience;

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- the effectiveness of education is improved due to independent and creative work of the student, as well as increased thinking skills and activity;
- keys used in the teaching process-stadia, presentations, cards, questions, guides, facilitates the organization of practical work and understanding of the subject;
- the student will have an expanded opportunity to take advantage of the latest achievements of science;
- conditions are created for self-control of the student;
- ensures the formation of the student as a specialist person at the expense of individual capabilities, mental potential, interests, etc.

In the system of school education, these pedagogical and digital technologies provide students with opportunities to prepare them for future professional activities as a result of increasing BCCS through the organization of educational processes. The use of these opportunities in pedagogical activity also embodies modern requirements for the knowledge and competence literacy of educators. The use of modern methods or computer programs that help to increase the effectiveness of teaching provides a solid foundation for students to become mature specialists in their future activities by increasing their interest in education, achieving logical, mental, creative thinking, etc.

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